

Utility-Driven Adaptive Model Selection for Digital Twinning

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Abstract

Digital twins have become central to modern engineering by providing interconnected virtual representations that mirror the behavior of physical assets. Their effectiveness, however, depends critically on the fidelity and efficiency of the underlying computational models used for decision support. This work introduces an adaptive Bayesian framework for quantifying and optimizing the operator-defined fidelity, efficiency, and overall utility of such virtual representations when approximating system responses in decision-oriented contexts. By integrating reduced-order models (ROMs) within a Bayesian inference and decision-theoretic setting, the framework identifies, at any point in time, the lowest-cost model capable of delivering an operator-defined level of predictive accuracy across operator-defined varying quantities of interest, while rigorously accounting for the uncertainty involved. The approach maximizes an operator-defined, purpose-related utility function that balances two competing attributes: (i) precision, reflecting the effect of over- or under-estimating target quantities on decision quality, and (ii) computational efficiency, ensuring feasibility for real-time inference. Leveraging assimilated monitoring data, the framework performs the optimal model selection recursively, enabling the virtual twin to evolve in tandem with the physical system. The resulting methodology supports automated decisions on whether to retain the current model, switch to an alternative resolution, or trigger retraining—thus establishing a pathway toward trustworthy digital twins for engineering decision support.

Keywords: Digital Twinning, Reduced Order Models, Bayesian Inference, uncertainty quantification

2 Glossary of Acronyms

cVAE conditional Variational AutoEncoder.

4 **DOF** Degree of Freedom.

FE Finite Element.

6 **FOM** Full Order Model.

HROM Hyper-Reduced Order Model.

8 **O&M** Operations and Maintenance.

QoI Quantity of Interest.

10 **ROM** Reduced Order Model.

SHM Structural Health Monitoring.

12 **UKF** Unscented Kalman Filter.

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1. Introduction

14 Structural infrastructure assets are inherently complex, featuring large-scale models, nonlinear dynamics, and
15 considerable uncertainty. As next-generation systems come to the forefront, there is a clear shift toward digital and
16 hybrid twin representations that provide virtual counterparts of physical assets [1, 2]. To clarify, although digital
17 twinning is a broad term spanning different disciplines, we here focus on physical assets with a structural behavior
18 that is represented by a dynamical system. The process of creating digital representations—commonly referred to as
19 virtualization or twinning—aims to replicate and interact with the behavior of real systems [3, 4]. To ensure such
20 virtual assets operate effectively, they typically rely on computational models that are both accurate and efficient.
21 Without this balance, real-time applications central to O&M, SHM, and decision support become infeasible [5, 6].

22 In the existing literature, numerous frameworks develop low-dimensional models or numerical surrogates as twin-
23 ning enablers [7, 8, 9]. Broadly, existing approaches fall into two categories: data-driven methods and physics-aware
24 methodologies. Data-driven models are particularly effective for systems with complex or chaotic dynamics. How-
25 ever, they often rely on ad hoc training procedures that capture only limited input–output relationships and tend to
26 degrade in performance under environmental or parametric variability. Moreover, such methods typically struggle
27 to extrapolate across time, input conditions, or spatial discretizations of the target system. Thus, many data-driven
28 surrogates remain problem-specific, mesh-dependent, and unable to generalize beyond the variable used for training
29 despite recent advancements [10, 11, 12, 13, 14]. These limitations might render them impractical for integration
30 into higher-level O&M or SHM frameworks, in which asset operators require flexibility when defining the QoIs and
31 task-specific support under changing requirements.

32 In contrast, physics-aware approaches preserve the internal structure of the dynamical system and embed physical
33 knowledge through explicit constraints or inductive biases within the virtual model [15, 16]. This improves inter-
34 pretability, stability, and accuracy in extrapolation and generalization tasks, thereby enhancing the applicability and re-
35 liability of the resulting digital representations for higher-level engineering workflows [17]. The effectiveness of such
36 strategies has been demonstrated in several studies, including [18, 19, 20, 21], where ROMs serve as forward simula-
37 tors in inverse problem settings for fault detection and input estimation in real time. Similarly, [22] employs stochastic
38 ROMs for damage detection in a mock-up aircraft wing, while [23, 24] showcases the integration of ROMs with the
39 UKF for system identification and uncertainty quantification under environmental and parametric variability. Beyond
40 model-based inference, related advances using physics-informed surrogates have also emerged [25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30].
41 Thus, our work focuses on model-based methodologies, which provide a structured, physics-grounded framework to
42 support engineering decisions across the O&M life-cycle of infrastructure assets [31, 32]. The core of such frame-
43 works lies in numerical models that condense complex systems into computationally tractable forms while retaining
44 their essential dynamic behavior, variability, and uncertainty.

45 Within this context, emerging frameworks focus on representations that adapt to changes of the underlying mon-
46 itored system. For instance, the state of the art regarding adaptivity and context-awareness in digital twinning is
47 discussed in detail in [33, 34, 35], which offer a generalized view on the concept of twinning and use abstract con-
48 cepts and suitable definitions to form a future road map. Data integration and the related challenges are discussed
49 in more detail in [36, 37]. Furthermore, adaptive twins are discussed in a contextualized manner in [38, 39, 40, 41],
50 where transfer learning is employed as an adaptation mechanism for machining systems while other noteworthy con-
51 tributions typically rely on purely data-driven techniques for updating the utilized models [42, 43, 44, 45, 46].

52 Similarly, several notable twinning works address engineering assets represented by dynamical systems. For
53 example, structural systems, concrete bridges, and underground infrastructure are addressed in [47, 48, 49, 50, 51,
54 52, 53] while many studies [54, 55, 56, 57] employ physics-based indicators to trigger model retraining or refinement
55 steps, often supported by data-driven enrichment in fracture problems. Other approaches, such as [58], introduce
56 ROM basis enrichment vector-space sieving and refinement trees for model adaptations. Extensions of this idea
57 address online model updates, either through basis compression [59] or additive low-rank updates [60]. Finally, active
58 learning [61, 62], reinforcement learning [63], and probabilistic schemes based on Gaussian Processes and Bayesian
59 networks [64, 65, 66, 67, 68] have been proposed.

60 Although adaptivity is frequently discussed within the digital twinning literature, existing approaches often address
61 it only partially, for example through offline retraining, manually triggered updates, static response thresholds, or task-
62 specific surrogate adaptation. Consequently, the literature still lacks, to the best of our knowledge, a formal operational
63 pipeline explaining how continuously evolving virtual representations should be orchestrated online under changing

64 monitoring data, changing operational objectives, and changing QoIs. Utility-guided schemes have been proposed
 elsewhere, eg. [69, 70, 71, 72, 73, 74, 75], without being linked with the virtualization of dynamical systems and the
 66 purpose of adaptive twinning or discussing the fidelity to efficiency balance, which is an inherent twinning tradeoff.

Figure 1: Graphical abstract of the adaptive model selection framework. Models of varying fidelity are integrated within a Bayesian decision-theoretic scheme that recursively assimilates monitoring data to select the optimal model that maximizes the operator-defined utility, ensuring an adaptive and efficient representation of the physical asset.

In contrast, the proposed framework formulates adaptive twinning as a recursive Bayesian decision-theoretic problem operating on parametrized physics-based model hierarchies. The framework continuously assimilates monitoring data and automatically selects the virtual representation that maximizes the operator-defined utility for the downstream task. Importantly, the utility itself may evolve during deployment, allowing the operator to redefine monitored QoIs, fidelity-efficiency trade-offs, and uncertainty requirements without retraining the underlying reduced-order models. The contribution therefore lies not in a standalone utility function or Bayesian formulation, but in the realization of a closed-loop adaptive orchestration framework that formally couples recursive inference, utility-driven decision-making, uncertainty propagation, and online model adaptation for operational digital twinning of dynamical systems.

Specifically, the proposed framework: (a) allows the operator to define task-dependent QoIs, monitoring setups, and utility functions, which cannot generally be assumed to be static or known *a priori* in real operational settings; (b) employs physics-based representations that admit a generic parametric formulation to deliver model-based response estimates across physical fields of interest, thus offering the flexibility required when defining QoIs and associated utilities; (c) formulates online recursive model selection within a Bayesian decision-theoretic framework, explicitly quantifying the utility of available models in terms of the value of information they provide for a given task; and (d) is designed to operate for large-scale structural dynamical systems under stochastic excitation and parametric variability. A methodological enabler is the use of the Unscented Transform for sampling the ROMs latent space and propagating uncertainty. The deterministic sigma-point expansion replaces Monte Carlo sampling, delivering the real-time uncertainty bounds essential to the utility-driven scheme. Thus, this work targets a fundamental and still largely unresolved challenge in operational digital twinning for dynamical systems: namely, how to formally construct and operate continuously evolving closed-loop virtual representations that adapt online to changing monitoring data, changing operational objectives, changing QoIs, and changing fidelity-efficiency requirements in a principled and automated manner [4]. In doing so, it establishes a pathway toward fit-for-purpose digital representations that maximize decision value and reliability throughout the asset's life-cycle [76].

90 We address the aforementioned challenges through an adaptive, data-informed framework that leverages contin-
 92 uous monitoring information to dynamically select the most suitable model given an operator defined utility. By
 94 evaluating a hierarchy of models with different levels of refinement and fidelity, the proposed approach also allows
 96 the virtual representation to update in tandem with the physical system. The candidate models—or virtual repre-
 98 sentations—can range from simplified analytical formulations to high-fidelity finite element models, each offering a
 100 different trade-off between accuracy, computational cost, and uncertainty. Effective model selection enables reliable
 102 and efficient decision-making for system design and operation by exploiting available monitoring data to continu-
 104 ously reduce uncertainty [77, 78, 79, 80]. Through Bayesian inference and the recursive assimilation of new informa-
 106 tion [81, 82], one can estimate the posterior uncertainty associated with each candidate model or resolution, thereby
 supporting data-informed and transparent decisions. Consequently, the model selection problem can be naturally for-
 mulated as a task of decision-making under uncertainty [83, 84]. The ultimate goal is to identify the fit-for-purpose
 model that offers the best balance between accuracy in recovering QoIs and computational efficiency. By recursively
 assimilating monitoring data, the framework adaptively tracks the evolving state of the physical asset and selects the
 model that maximizes expected utility, balancing prediction accuracy and computational efficiency for real-time ap-
 plications. As illustrated in Figure 1, the method autonomously decides whether to retain the current model, switch to
 another, or trigger retraining—thus enabling adaptive, uncertainty-aware digital twins tailored to the decision context.

106 The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: In section 2, the methodological components of the framework
 are presented including the reduced-order modeling techniques employed to derive the pretrained model resolutions
 108 in Figure 1 and the Bayesian decision-theoretic approach to model selection. In section 3, we describe the numerical
 case studies and results that highlight the efficiency and effectiveness of the proposed framework. Lastly, section 4
 110 summarizes our contributions, discusses limitations, and offers directions for future research.

2. Methodology

112 The methodological components of the proposed framework highlighted in Figure 1 are described herein and then
 summarized in its training mode reported in Algorithm 1 and its deployment mode in Algorithm 2. First, models at
 114 different resolutions are assembled. This process is conducted offline and is part of the training stage. Each resolution
 defines a unique balance between computational speed and predictive accuracy. Three resolutions are exemplified in
 116 our work: a) The full-order FE model of the system, termed FOM, which serves as the highest-resolution representa-
 tion considered in the model hierarchy and has higher potential for precision, b) ROMs that strike a balance between
 118 precision and efficiency, and c) HROMs, which correspond to the ROMs equipped with hyper-reduction, thus offering
 the highest efficiency. The ROMs populating the second resolution differ in their dimension $\{r\}$, which defines their
 120 complexity and leads to varying efficiency-to-fidelity tradeoffs. Similarly, the HROMs populating the last resolution
 are regulated by parameters $\{\tau, r\}$, where $\{\tau\}$ controls the hyper-reduction resolution. Conceptually, a very large value
 122 for $\{r\}$ renders a ROM equivalent to the FOM with respect to the sought balance, and the equivalent applies for the
 HROMs. In practice, the achieved balance granularity is well-separated between the defined resolutions, which fur-
 124 ther highlights the need to select the optimal model given a downstream task. Second, Bayesian filtering is employed
 to navigate the fidelity-to-efficiency trade-off, update the underlying models, and determine the optimal one given
 126 an operator-defined utility. This is part of the online operational stage of the proposed framework summarized in
 Algorithm 2. The following subsections describe the assembly of the considered model resolutions and outline the
 128 Bayesian decision-theoretic approach used for model selection.

2.1. Full Order Model - FOM

130 We assume availability of a FOM, which corresponds to a FE model that is suitable for nonlinear structural
 dynamics simulations. The corresponding dynamical system is dependent on the input vector $\mathbf{p} = [p_1, \dots, p_{n_p}]^T \in \Omega \subset$
 132 \mathbb{R}^{n_p} , which captures all n_p system- and excitation-relevant parameters and is described by the following governing
 equations:

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\mathbf{u}}(t) + \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{u}(t), \dot{\mathbf{u}}(t), \mathbf{p}) = \mathbf{F}(t, \mathbf{p}), \quad (1)$$

134 where $\mathbf{u}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ denotes the response in terms of displacements, $\mathbf{M} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ the mass matrix, and $\mathbf{F}(t, \mathbf{p}) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ the
 induced excitation. For simplicity, the parametric dependence of the mass matrix is omitted. Nonlinear behavior
 136 is captured through the restoring force term $\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{u}(t), \dot{\mathbf{u}}(t), \mathbf{p}) \in \mathbb{R}^n$, which may represent effects such as plasticity,

138 hysteresis, or interface nonlinearities, depending on the system response and parameter vector \mathbf{p} . The full-order dimension n defines the size of the coordinate space—and thus the total number of degrees of freedom—governing the model’s computational cost, as numerical operations scale with n .

140 2.2. Reduced and Hyper-Reduced Order Models (ROMs & HROMs)

142 2.2.1. Projection-based model order reduction

142 The reduction approach employed herein begins with a Galerkin projection scheme, with more general extensions such as the Petrov–Galerkin method discussed in [85, 86]. As outlined in section 1, a physics-based reduction is 144 adopted to enhance interpretability and applicability within higher-level SHM frameworks. The proposed approach assumes that the solution of Equation (1) resides in a low-dimensional subspace of rank $r \ll n$, where n is the full-order dimension. Accordingly, the system response can be expressed as: 146

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{p}) \approx \mathbf{V}(\mathbf{p})\mathbf{q} \quad (2)$$

148 where $\mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$ represents the projection basis that expresses the aforementioned subspace of the ROM and $\mathbf{q} \in \mathbb{R}^r$ is the low-order coordinate vector. Via substitution of \mathbf{u} into Equation (1) and after multiplying the governing set with \mathbf{u}^T , thus performing a Galerkin projection, the following can be derived:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{M}}\ddot{\mathbf{q}}(t) + \tilde{\mathbf{g}}(\dot{\mathbf{q}}, \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}) = \tilde{\mathbf{F}}(\mathbf{p}, t) \quad (3)$$

150 where $\tilde{\mathbf{M}} = \mathbf{V}^T \mathbf{M} \mathbf{V}$, $\tilde{\mathbf{g}} = \mathbf{V}^T \mathbf{g}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{F}} = \mathbf{V}^T \mathbf{F}$. Several techniques exist for constructing the projection basis \mathbf{V} [87]. In this work, the Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) is employed, using a set of FOM simulations over a training 152 parameter space to assemble the solution snapshots as:

$$\hat{\mathbf{S}} = \left[\hat{\mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{p}_1) \quad \hat{\mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{p}_2) \quad \dots \quad \hat{\mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{p}_{N_s}) \right] \quad (4)$$

154 where $\hat{\mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{p}_i) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n_t}$ contains the displacement time history for a given parametric realization \mathbf{p}_i , henceforth termed as a snapshot, and, as a result, $\hat{\mathbf{S}} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times (n_t \times n_s)}$ is termed the snapshot matrix. The variable n_t represents the number of simulation (time) steps and n_s is the total number of snapshots. Via Singular Value Decomposition of $\hat{\mathbf{S}}$ the ROM 156 projection basis can be assembled as follows

$$\hat{\mathbf{S}} = \mathbf{\Lambda} \mathbf{\Sigma} \mathbf{Z}^T \quad (5)$$

and after truncating $\mathbf{\Lambda}$:

$$\mathbf{V} = \left[\mathbf{\Lambda}_1 \quad \mathbf{\Lambda}_2 \quad \dots \quad \mathbf{\Lambda}_r \right] \quad (6)$$

158 where $\mathbf{\Lambda}_i$ is the i column of matrix $\mathbf{\Lambda}$. Since the low-order dimension of Equation (2) is defined as r , the above truncation is applied to obtain the first r components of \mathbf{V} . The reduced order r reflects the balance between the 160 expected reconstruction accuracy and the model’s efficiency. It is typically obtained using a suitable error measure such as the singular value decay. In this work, we derive ROMs of various orders and address the fidelity-to-efficiency balance via a user-defined utility that guides the model selection to output the optimal model for a downstream task. 162 The reduced dimension $r \ll n$ implies that the linearized Equation (3) is solved at the reduced order r . However, the nonlinear term $\tilde{\mathbf{g}}$ still requires assembly over the full mesh, with cost scaling with the number of elements n_e . 164 This residual dependence on the underlying mesh size constitutes the dominant computational bottleneck of standard ROMs and motivates the hyper-reduction step discussed in section 2.2.4. 166

2.2.2. VpROM: A conditional Variational Autoencoder (cVAE)-boosted ROM

168 The dynamic behavior of the system, governed by the equations in Equation (1), is highly dependent on the parameter vector \mathbf{p} . Attempting a projection-based reduction with a single basis, as described in Equation (2), might 170 result in a prohibitively large dimension r and ROMs that prove inefficient. To handle parametric variability, a common strategy is to construct a set of local projection bases \mathbf{V}_i , each derived from FOM snapshots $\hat{\mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{p}_i)$ corresponding to 172 a specific parameter realization \mathbf{p}_i . Subsequent interpolation [88, 89] or clustering [90] methods can be used to approximate the system responses at unseen parameter values. Specifically, the two-stage process introduced in [91]

174 is used in this work to introduce parametric variability at the ROM level. First, a collection of local bases is obtained and the following system is solved in the least-squares sense:

$$\mathbf{V}_i(\mathbf{p}_i) = \mathbf{V}_{global} * \mathbf{X}_i(\mathbf{p}_i) \quad (7)$$

176 where $\mathbf{V}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$ is an instance of the collection of local bases, $\mathbf{V}_{global} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times \tilde{r}}$ captures the dynamics across the entire domain and $\mathbf{X}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{\tilde{r} \times r}$ is a coefficient matrix. \tilde{r} signifies the total number of truncated modes retained on \mathbf{V}_{global} and can be treated similarly to r . Second, interpolation is performed on the coefficient matrices \mathbf{X}_i . These comprise a reduced size ($\tilde{r} \ll n$), thus removing any dependency on the FOM dimension n . After interpolating the coefficient matrices 180 \mathbf{X}_i , the corresponding local ROM basis \mathbf{V}_q can be obtained for any validation parametric sample \mathbf{p}_q . Following the suggestions in [91] the local bases \mathbf{V} are first projected to the tangent space of the Grassmannian manifold, where the interpolation operations performed output a local basis that retains key properties like orthogonality [92, 93, 94]. 182 Alternatively, a re-orthogonalization step can be performed.

184 Building upon prior work by the authors [95, 96], the proposed framework employs a cVAE as a nonlinear generative model to learn a smooth, generalizable mapping between parameters and the basis coefficients \mathbf{X} . The cVAE acts as a nonlinear generator and approximator of the coefficient matrices \mathbf{X} , and consequently of the local projection subspaces \mathbf{V} and associated ROMs. Parametric variability is incorporated directly at the ROM level by conditioning the cVAE on known system parameters or on features derived from measured responses. In previous formulations [95], the *VpROM* was designed in a generalized manner, assuming no prior knowledge of the true parameter vector \mathbf{p} during 190 training or deployment; instead, the cVAE infers the local basis from observed response features. When the parameters \mathbf{p} are known or can be inferred they can directly serve as conditioning inputs, which is the case here that parameter inference is handled via Bayesian filtering. Finally, the probabilistic nature of the cVAE allows the *VpROM* to quantify uncertainty: the latent space is a learned probability distribution and its sampling enables uncertainty propagation 192 through the ROM, yielding error bounds on the predicted response.

Figure 2: The architecture of the employed cVAE. The parameter vector \mathbf{p} is treated as the conditioning feature, which is concatenated both with the input vector \mathbf{X} and the latent space \mathbf{Z} .

196 The *VpROM* framework is illustrated in Figure 2. Formally, the encoder learns the conditional distribution $q_\theta(\mathbf{Z}|\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{p})$, while the decoder reconstructs the data via $p_\phi(\mathbf{X}|\mathbf{Z}, \mathbf{p})$. Accordingly, the system variability in Equation (1) is represented by \mathbf{p} , and the mapping from \mathbf{p} to the local bases \mathbf{V} in Equation (3) is learned through the relationship between \mathbf{p} and the reduced coefficient matrices \mathbf{X} in Equation (7). Once trained, the conditional VAE 198 serves as a generative model capable of sampling the reduced basis coefficients \mathbf{X}_i defined in Equation (7). Given an inferred parameter realization $\hat{\mathbf{p}}$ from Bayesian inference, samples drawn from the latent distribution are decoded to generate the corresponding \mathbf{X} values. In this work, a diagonal Gaussian prior is adopted for the latent space, as depicted in Figure 3. 200 202

2.2.3. Uncertainty Bounds via the Unscented Transform

204 Once the decoder is trained, predictions are obtained by sampling the inferred variational distribution of the latent space and decoding these samples. A realization of the random variable ϵ is first drawn and transformed into \mathbf{Z}

Figure 3: Architecture of the cVAE in basis generation mode: The prior distribution ϵ is sampled, and the latent vectors are taken after concatenating with the (inferred) vector $\hat{\mathbf{p}}$. Dimensionality serves only illustrative purposes.

206 using the deterministic mean μ_θ and standard deviation σ_θ inferred by the encoder. The latent vector \mathbf{Z} is then concatenated with the inferred parameters $\hat{\mathbf{p}}$ and passed through the decoder to generate samples from $p_\phi(\hat{\mathbf{X}}|\mathbf{Z}, \mathbf{p})$ —each
 208 representing a possible realization of the reduced coefficients \mathbf{X} . By repeating this process, the mean and variance of the estimated coefficients and projection bases can be evaluated. Subsequent parallel simulations for the ROMs and
 210 HROMs enable uncertainty propagation from the latent space to the output response. The resulting ensemble statistics yield numerical error bounds that quantify prediction uncertainty, as demonstrated in [95, 96].

212 However, the sampling procedure described above can be computationally expensive, as hundreds of samples may be required to capture the system’s response uncertainty. To improve efficiency, we adopt the Unscented Transform
 214 (UT) [97], which exploits the Gaussian nature of the latent distributions to generate a deterministic set of sigma points instead of numerous random samples. These sigma points are propagated through the decoder, and the resulting
 216 outputs are combined using predefined weights that preserve the mean and covariance of the original Gaussian distribution, yielding accurate and efficient uncertainty estimates.

218 2.2.4. Hyper-reduction

The HROMs are assembled by equipping the derived ROMs with hyper-reduction [98]. Hyper-reduction provides
 220 a second-level approximation that alleviates the computational cost of updating and reconstructing the nonlinear term $\tilde{\mathbf{g}}$ in Equation (3). Here, we employ the Energy Conserving Mesh Sampling and Weighting (ECSW) method [99, 100],
 222 a well-established physics-based technique. In brief, ECSW relies on a sparse weighted reconstruction of $\tilde{\mathbf{g}}$ along a subset of FE elements. Given an underlying FE discretization of n_e elements represented by the set E , the nonlinear
 224 term $\tilde{\mathbf{g}}$ and the (tangent) stiffness matrix $\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ typically required in structural dynamics can be approximated given a vector of reduced coordinates \mathbf{q} via a weighted sum over a subset $\tilde{E} \subset E$ of the total elements n_e using the
 226 following FE-like formulation

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\mathbf{g}}(\mathbf{q}) &\approx \sum_{\tilde{E} \subset E} \xi_e \mathbf{V}^T \mathbf{L}_e^T \mathbf{g}_e(\mathbf{L}_e \mathbf{V} \mathbf{q}) \\ \tilde{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{q}) &\approx \sum_{\tilde{E} \subset E} \xi_e \mathbf{V}^T \mathbf{L}_e^T \mathbf{K}_e(\mathbf{L}_e \mathbf{V} \mathbf{q}) \mathbf{L}_e \mathbf{V} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{L}_e \in \mathbb{R}^{n_d \times n}$ is a Boolean selection matrix to subset the basis \mathbf{V} to the DOFs associated with element e , n_d is the
 228 number of DOFs for element e , \mathbf{g}_e denotes the nonlinear contribution of element e , $\tilde{\mathbf{K}}$ is the reduced-order counter part of the tangent stiffness matrix \mathbf{K} and ξ_e are non-negative weights assigned to the element e . Thus, \tilde{E} and ξ are
 230 obtained via solving a constrained minimization problem so that the difference between the total work over the entire meshed domain and the corresponding sparse weighted approximation using the reduced mesh is minimized over a
 232 set of training configurations. This process is regulated by a residual tolerance τ that controls the size of k , and thus the accuracy of the resulting approximation.

Algorithm 1 The training mode of the proposed framework.

Training - Offline Stage

Assumes availability of a high-fidelity FE model serving as a (parametrized) FOM

Modeling parametric traits are encoded into the parameter vector \mathbf{p} (Eq. 1)

- 1: Generate N_s training samples for the parameter vector \mathbf{p}
- 2: **for** $i=1, \dots, N_s$ **do**
- 3: Simulate the FOM for \mathbf{p}_i and obtain snapshot $\mathbf{U}_i(\mathbf{p}_i)$ (Eq. 4)
- 4: Store all internal, *ECSW*-relevant variables during intermediate solver iterations (Eq. 8)
- 5: Obtain the local reduced bases \mathbf{V}_i for the ROMs (Eq. 5-6)
- 6: **end for**
- 7: Obtain the global basis \mathbf{V}_{global} (Eq. 5-6)
- 8: **for** $j=1, \dots, N_s$ **do**
- 9: Compute coefficient matrix \mathbf{X}_j (Eq. 7)
- 10: **end for**
- 11: Compute the element subset \tilde{E} and the weights ξ for *ECSW* to obtain the HROMs (Sec. 2.2.4)
- 12: Train the cVAE component for local basis generation (Fig. 2)
- 13: Tune the UKF parameters using noise-polluted data from FOM validation runs

Testing data generation

Assumes availability of a sufficiently **perturbed** FE model serving as the **perturbed** FOM

Parametric traits varying during operation are encoded into vector $\boldsymbol{\mu} \subseteq \mathbf{p}$

- 1: Generate N_q testing samples for the parameter vector $\boldsymbol{\mu}$
 - 2: **for** $i=1, \dots, N_q$ **do**
 - 3: Simulate the **perturbed** FOM for $\boldsymbol{\mu}_i$ and obtain the acceleration time histories
 - 4: Sub-select only the time histories of the monitored DOFs and pollute them with noise
 - 5: **end for**
-

234 The residual tolerance τ typically admits a relatively narrow range of meaningful values: very loose tolerances
235 yield HROMs of insufficient fidelity, while very tight tolerances forfeit the efficiency benefit of hyper-reduction. The
236 values $\tau \in \{10^{-2}, 10^{-3}\}$ employed in the case studies are representative of this tradeoff while suboptimal choices
237 of τ are absorbed by the proposed framework, since each $\{\tau, r\}$ combination yields an additional candidate model
238 resolution that is automatically penalized by the utility-driven selection mechanism if its fidelity-to-efficiency tradeoff
239 is unfavorable for the downstream task.

240 **2.3. A Bayesian decision-theoretic approach to model selection**

241 The framework outlined in the previous section can be employed to generate the different model resolutions to
242 assist with decision-making and SHM tasks, as illustrated in Figure 1. As physical infrastructure assets evolve over
243 time, a challenge emerges: determining the lowest-cost model capable of achieving an operator-defined predictive
244 accuracy for a given engineering context. To capture this, the utility formulation adopted in this work follows the
245 principles of Bayesian decision theory, where the objective is to select the model that maximizes the expected utility
246 for a given decision-making task [101]. In this context, the utility function reflects the preferences and operational
247 priorities of the asset operator rather than a quantity derived solely from the model structure. Consequently, the utility
248 is intentionally treated as an operator-defined input that can vary depending on the downstream task, the quantities of
249 interest (QoIs), and the computational constraints of the application.

250 In the present manuscript, the utility is exemplified through a weighted combination of two key attributes that are
251 particularly relevant for dynamic response prediction models:

- 252 1. Model fidelity, in terms of recovering target QoIs, and
- 253 2. Computational cost required to generate these predictions

254 These attributes represent two fundamental and often competing objectives when deploying numerical surrogates
255 or reduced-order models for monitoring and decision-support applications. The framework then performs model

256 selection by identifying the model resolution that maximizes the operator-defined utility. Importantly, the framework
 258 itself does not aim to optimize or learn the utility function; rather, it provides a mechanism for selecting the most
 260 suitable model among available alternatives given the utility specified by the operator. This design choice reflects
 practical engineering scenarios, where decision criteria and performance priorities are typically defined externally
 based on operational requirements.

Let θ denote the random vector of uncertain model parameters. For simplicity, we assume these coincide with
 262 the modeling parameters of the considered models in Eqs. 1, 3, and Figure 3, i.e., $\theta = \hat{\mathbf{p}}$. This assumption is not
 restrictive—the framework remains valid provided $\theta \subseteq \mathbf{p}$. Hence, the model parametrization introduced in section 2.2
 264 is kept intentionally general, as the parameter vector directly governs model selection. In turn, a prior probabilistic
 model $\pi_{\text{pr}}(\hat{\mathbf{p}})$ needs to be assigned. The incoming signals, collectively denoted as monitoring data \mathbf{d} , can be leveraged
 266 to perform Bayesian inference for model updating, which outputs the posterior distribution of $\hat{\mathbf{p}}$ given \mathbf{d} , denoted by
 $\pi_{\text{pos}}(\hat{\mathbf{p}}|\mathbf{d})$. The optimal model to be selected M_{opt} conditional on the monitoring data \mathbf{d} can be then obtained as:

$$M_{\text{opt}|\mathbf{d}} = \underset{\{M_1, M_2, \dots, M_n\}}{\text{argmax}} \mathbb{E}_{\hat{\mathbf{p}}|\mathbf{d}, M_i} [U_i], \quad (9)$$

$$\text{where } U_i = U(\text{fidelity}|M_i, \text{efficiency}|M_i, \hat{\mathbf{p}}|M_i)$$

268 where U is the considered utility function that relates the uncertain parameter vector $\hat{\mathbf{p}}$ and models M , thus mapping
 possible outcomes to their utility as illustrated in Figure 4. The expectation \mathbb{E} in Equation (9) is evaluated with respect
 270 to the posterior distribution $\pi_{\text{pos}}(\hat{\mathbf{p}}|\mathbf{y}, M_i)$. The possible decisions are summarized in the set $\{M_1, M_2, \dots, M_k\}$ in the
 case of k competing models, where M_i represents the decision to employ the i -th model for inferring the parameter
 272 and recovering the dynamic behavior of the engineered system of interest.

As discussed, two competing attributes are used to exemplify the utility function U in this work: model fidelity and
 274 computational efficiency. Illustrative examples of the resulting utility branches are shown in Figure 4. In Figure 4a
 the considered utility curve with respect to the ability of the model to recover the quantity of interest is depicted,
 276 also accounting for over- and under-estimation effects. Underestimation of quantities of interest is here penalized
 more as it might lead to unexpected failures and catastrophic events, which are considered more critical in asset
 278 management compared to potential additional costs caused by overestimation. Since Bayesian filtering is employed
 for parameter estimation, the utility with respect to the model's precision is evaluated using readings from redundant
 280 sensor measurements that are not employed on the inference of $\hat{\mathbf{p}}$. In Figure 4b the implemented relationship between
 the evaluation time of the model and its utility is reported. The model runtime is evaluated per 1 second input
 282 excitation. The overall utility can be computed as a weighted combination of the competing attributes, allowing the
 decision-maker to weigh the considered attributes according to the decision at hand. The corresponding mathematical
 284 formulation reads:

$$U_i(\text{fidelity}|M_i, \text{efficiency}|M_i, \hat{\mathbf{p}}|M_i) = \gamma * U_i(\text{fidelity}|M_i, \hat{\mathbf{p}}|M_i) + (1 - \gamma) * U_i(\text{efficiency}|M_i, \hat{\mathbf{p}}|M_i) \quad (10)$$

$$U_i(\text{fidelity}|M_i, \hat{\mathbf{p}}|M_i) = \begin{cases} 1 - w_1 * \left(\frac{y_f - \hat{y}_f}{y_f}\right)^2 * (w_1 * \epsilon_{\text{max}})^{-1}, & (y_f - \hat{y}_f) > 0 \\ 1 - w_2 * \left(\frac{y_f - \hat{y}_f}{y_f}\right)^2 * (w_2 * \epsilon_{\text{max}})^{-1}, & (y_f - \hat{y}_f) \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

$$U_i(\text{efficiency}|M_i, \hat{\mathbf{p}}|M_i) = 1 - \frac{\log^2(1 + t_{M_i})}{\log^2(t_{\text{max}})} \quad (12)$$

286 where y_f denotes the observed values for the QoI and \hat{y} the model-approximated ones using the inferred $\hat{\mathbf{p}}$ and the
 selected model resolution M_i . The variable t_{M_i} denotes the evaluation time of model resolution M_i per second of
 excitation input, t_{max} is the maximum acceptable evaluation time that corresponds to zero utility and ϵ_{max} the maximum
 288 prediction error that is penalized with zero utility. As highlighted in Figure 1, the framework is driven by online
 Bayesian inference and allows the asset operator to define either the full utility function, or the weights w_1, w_2, γ
 290 that account for over- and underestimation effects and the importance of the competing attributes. This flexibility is
 powered by online integration of sensing data and the model-driven nature of the proposed scheme that relies in the
 292 ability of the underlying ROMs and HROMs to approximate QoIs in all response fields and spatial locations. This is
 critical for the serviceability in different downstream tasks with varying utility requirements. Here, the weights w_1, w_2

(a) Utility as a function of the model's fidelity.

(b) Utility as a function of the model runtime.

Figure 4: Example utility functions for the considered competing attributes, namely i) model fidelity, which accounts for over/under-estimating target quantities, and (ii) computational runtime to ensure real-time inference when possible.

294 are chosen to account for over- and under-estimation effects ($w_1 > w_2$) and to normalize the computed discrepancy so
 295 that the maximum utility is equal to 1, as illustrated in Figure 4, where $w_1 = 3$, $w_2 = 1$, $t_{max} = 100s$, $\epsilon_{max} = 20\%$.

296 It is worth noting that the utility-function parameters γ , w_1 , w_2 , ϵ_{max} , and t_{max} are not internal parameters of the
 297 framework, but inputs supplied by the operator to encode the preferences and criticality of the downstream task. The
 298 framework remains flexible to the specific utility form and provides the mechanism for selecting the optimal model
 299 given any operator-defined utility. In the same spirit, the retraining trigger is treated as an operator-defined input; a
 300 working value of $U < 0.75$ has been adopted in the case studies and proves robust under the utility forms employed.
 301 More specifically, since efficiency tends to be less sensitive, the retraining threshold can be set by identifying the
 302 fidelity utility level deemed unacceptable for the downstream task and propagating it through Equation (10). For
 303 instance, a fidelity utility of approximately 0.5 combined with a near-unit efficiency utility yields $U \approx 0.75$ under
 304 balanced weighting ($\gamma = 0.5$), which matches the empirical heuristic adopted in the numerical demonstrations.

305 The UKF is employed for parameter inference, given its scalability and real-time capabilities. Regarding imple-
 306 mentation, the UKF is adapted from the open-source repository and tutorials offered in [102, 103]. The discrepancy
 307 between the measured acceleration signals \mathbf{y} and the model-predicted responses $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$ is employed as the residual term in
 308 the corresponding likelihood functions driving the inference algorithms. The methodological components introduced
 in this section are integrated into an operational pipeline summarized in Algorithms 1 & 2.

Algorithm 2 The deployment mode of the proposed framework.

Deployment - Online Mode

Assumes availability of acceleration monitoring signals for a testing sample μ_q

Asset Operator: Defines utility function or importance weights of competing attributes (Eq. 10-12).

- 1: **while** (monitoring sequence is incoming) **OR for** (every t seconds)
 - 2: Use previous inferred quantities as priors (if available)
 - 3: Perform (recursive) state & parameter identification for every model resolution except the FOM via the UKF
 - 4: Update models to compute QoIs and utility U using the posterior estimates
 - 5: Select the optimal model that minimizes utility U **OR** Initiate FOM runs & retraining event
 - 6: **end while/for**
 - 7: Sample the cVAE-latent space of the selected model using the UKF estimates (Fig. 3 & Sec. 2.2.3)
 - 8: Evaluate the selected optimal model for every sample (in parallel) to obtain error bounds in the QoIs
 - 9: Use the selected optimal model for the downstream task at hand
-

310 3. Numerical case studies

312 The proposed framework is validated in two structural dynamics case studies, involving hysteretic and geometric nonlinearities. In both cases, the approach performs recursive model selection to identify the optimal resolution for structural assets whose state, parameters, and health condition evolve over time. The considered model resolutions are summarized in Table 1. Via varying the reduced-order r and the hyper-reduction regulation parameter τ different ROM and HROM granularity levels are derived, reflecting different fidelity-to-efficiency tradeoffs. Larger dimensions r are not considered as the UKF dimension becomes prohibitively large for real-time inference.

Table 1: Reference table for the considered model resolutions.

Reference name	Description
FOM	The full-order Finite Element model according to section 2
ROMs	The $VpROM$ according to section 2 with varying reduced-order $r \in \{4, 8, 16\}$.
HROMs	The $VpROM$ additionally equipped with hyper-reduction and varying $\{\tau, r\}$
Perturbed FOM	The FOM with a finer mesh and perturbed material properties. Used for generating response signals with a 10% noise level for testing.

318 In the absence of experimental measurements, a perturbed FOM is introduced to emulate realistic discrepancies between the training models and the monitored system. This approach is commonly used in model validation studies to avoid the inverse crime and to introduce controlled model mismatch between training and testing environments [104, 320 105]. The specific perturbations considered in this work reflect typical sources of uncertainty encountered in structural monitoring applications. Specifically, variations in Young’s modulus are widely used in model updating studies to represent uncertainties in material properties or structural degradation. In addition, modifying the spatial distribution of these parameters allows the introduction of localized discrepancies that mimic model-form errors or unmodeled structural effects. Measurement noise is also added to the response signals in order to represent the noise levels commonly observed in vibration monitoring systems. Although the exact perturbation magnitudes are not meant to represent a particular experimental campaign, they were selected to introduce a meaningful level of model discrepancy while remaining within ranges typically encountered in structural monitoring applications. Importantly, the proposed framework does not rely on the perturbed FOM being an exact representation of reality. Instead, the underlying models are parametrized and can adapt to uncertain inputs through the Bayesian inference stage, as demonstrated in what follows. When model discrepancies become significant and the predictive performance of the available models deteriorates, the proposed utility-based selection mechanism is designed to identify this condition and signal the need for model retraining or enrichment. Thus, the perturbed FOM adopts the following measures:

- The perturbed FOM employs a finer finite element mesh than the in-house FOM used to train the ROMs.
- 334 • The Young’s modulus E is randomly perturbed, with element-wise values drawn from a normal distribution with mean E_{ref} and standard deviation 3% of E_{ref} .
- 336 • The density ρ is randomly perturbed, with element-wise values drawn from a normal distribution with mean ρ_{ref} and standard deviation 3% of ρ_{ref}
- 338 • Measurement noise corresponding to 10% of the root-mean-square (RMS) value of each signal is added.

340 The performance of the proposed framework in parameter and response inference is assessed by reproducing the time-history response of selected quantities of interest or their spatial distribution at specific simulation snapshots. Parameter inference is based on vibration measurements from accelerometers assumed to be installed on the perturbed FOM of the structure. For the model selection task, the utility is evaluated using data from redundant sensors not involved in the inference process, potentially including other quantities of interest such as stresses or displacements. 342 The specific monitoring and inference configurations are detailed separately for each case study.

344 All computations are performed on the Euler High Performance Cluster of ETH Zurich using in-house FE and UKF codes in a parallelized setup when possible. Reported speed-up factors refer solely to the online evaluation phase, are averaged over all model evaluations and exclude the offline training cost of the models. The model speed-up is computed as $t_{\text{FOM}}/t_{\text{ROM}}$, where t denotes the model evaluation time.

3.1. Benchmark Shear Frame with Hysteretic Links

As an initial example, we consider an open-source, benchmark multi-degree of freedom nonlinear response simulator of a three-dimensional shear frame with nodal couplings that exhibit Bouc-Wen hysteresis, available in [106].

3.1.1. Decision support scenario

The following case study that requires decision-making under an adaptive model deployment is defined: An asset operator needs SHM-related support for a number of example decisions that require varying levels of accuracy in different QoIs. Specifically, the asset operator defines a balanced utility function at first, assuming no damage has occurred. After damage events start occurring, the operator switches to a utility that favors efficiency and fast decisions related to proactive actions, e.g. evacuation. Then, they decide to further modify the utility function to favor accuracy and obtain insight in internal structural quantities such as stresses that define the asset’s load-bearing capacity. This setup is summarized in Table 2 and an example scenario is discussed later in Figure 6.

The monitored structure is a shear frame representing a structural asset, like a hospital building, and experiences ground motion reflecting an earthquake scenario [107]. This demonstrative example is chosen due to the relevance of the simulator to real-life infrastructure assets and its inherent ability to parametrically model multiple simultaneously activated instances of nonlinearity, representing damage in different regions. The proposed framework is utilized to identify the optimal model that maximizes the input utility at any given time.

Table 2: Details of the monitoring setup for the shear frame. Damage events are modeled by varying the parameter vector μ as shown in Figure 6. The max stress is evaluated in rolling windows of 0.5 seconds.

Scenario	Frame gets damaged (multiple events, unevenly) due to ground motion.
Objective	Input utility changes to reflect different downstream tasks. Given an operator defined utility, select the optimal model to be used for related SHM tasks at any given time.
Utility function(s)	Equations 10-12, Figure 4, $t_{max} = 6s$, $w_1 = 3$, $w_2 = 1$, $\epsilon_{max} = 35\%$
Utility function variations	Example damage event A $\rightarrow \gamma = 0.5$, QoI=Inter-story drift Example damage events B&C $\rightarrow \gamma = 0.3$, QoI=Inter-story drift Example damage event D $\rightarrow \gamma = 0.8$, QoI=Maximum stress at supports Example damage event X $\rightarrow \gamma = 0.5$, QoI=Inter-story drift
Monitoring data for inference	Nodal accelerations Six nodes monitored (blue crosses in Fig. 5a)

3.1.2. Numerical model setup

A schematic of the shear frame setup is shown in Figure 5a, where the colored columns indicate regions subjected to damage. Regarding material properties, steel HEA cross sections are used for all beam elements, and the structure is assembled using two frames along the x -axis, each of length $l = 5.5$ m length and width $w = 3$ m. All stories have a height of $h = 3$ m. All joints in Figure 5a are modeled using the Bouc-Wen hysteretic formulation, a smooth nonlinear model widely used to represent material hysteresis [108]. Following the benchmark in [106], a Bouc-Wen model is implemented at each DOF of every nodal link to simulate the total restoring force \mathbf{R} . An illustration of the nonlinear mechanism along the longitudinal x -DOF is provided in Figure 5b. \mathbf{R} is expressed as the superposition of linear and nonlinear terms, represented by the two springs in Figure 5b, and depends on the instantaneous nodal displacement δu and its hysteretic component z . The vectorized governing equations are given as:

$$\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{R}_{\text{linear}} + \mathbf{R}_{\text{hysteretic}} = \alpha k \mathbf{d}u + (1 - \alpha)kz \quad (13)$$

where $\mathbf{d}u$ represents the nodal displacement, α denotes the characteristic post-yield to elastic stiffness ratio, and k is the corresponding stiffness coefficient of the link. The variable \mathbf{z} represents the hysteretic portion of the elongation,

or displacement in general, and controls the hysteretic forcing. It obeys the following

$$\dot{\mathbf{z}} = \frac{A\mathbf{d}\dot{\mathbf{u}} - \nu(t)(\beta|\mathbf{d}\dot{\mathbf{u}}|\mathbf{z}|^{w-1} - \gamma\mathbf{d}\dot{\mathbf{u}}|\mathbf{z}|^w)}{\eta(t)} \quad (14)$$

$$\nu(t) = 1.0 + \delta_\nu \epsilon(t), \quad \eta(t) = 1.0 + \delta_\eta \epsilon(t), \quad \epsilon(t) = \int_0^t \mathbf{z} \mathbf{d}\dot{\mathbf{u}} dt \quad (15)$$

where the shape, smoothness, and amplitude of the hysteretic curve that characterizes the dynamic behavior of each joint are determined by parameters β , γ , w , and A . Their absolute values are not of interest, but rather their sums or differences, which may indicate a hardening or softening relationship [109, 110]. The terms $\nu(t)$ and $\eta(t)$ are introduced to capture strength deterioration and stiffness degradation effects via the corresponding coefficients δ_ν and δ_η . In turn, their evolution in time depends on the absorbed hysteretic energy $\epsilon(t)$.

(a) Illustration of the shear frame.

(b) Bouc-Wen model in the x -DOF.

Figure 5: Schematic of the shear frame and link mechanism. The colored columns of the first, second, and third floor mark regions where damage is introduced. Blue crosses denote sensor locations.

The frame is further subjected to base excitation representing seismic loading. Base accelerograms are applied at an angle of $\theta = \pi/4$ relative to the longitudinal axis. During training, ROMs and HROMs are generated using weighted combinations of the Kobe, Morgan, Northridge, and El Centro seismogram [111].

The employed monitoring scheme summarized in Table 2 uses six acceleration sensors at different nodes indicated via blue crosses in Figure 5a. These nodes have been chosen to ensure observability and showcase the performance of the proposed framework under limited output measurements and are positioned without utilizing any optimization schemes. A more realistic setup could utilize the underlying models for optimal positioning, potentially improving the performance of the inference algorithms. Each sensor records acceleration in both the longitudinal and vertical directions, and these data are used for the parameter inference task described in Figure 1. The top-story inter-story drift and the stresses at the supports are also assumed to be monitored and serves as measures that quantify model precision within the model selection framework summarized in Table 2. This choice is motivated by the strong correlation between the monitored QoIs and the structural integrity and seismic resilience of frame systems, making them a key indicator for both design and condition monitoring [112, 113]. Alternatively, data from a redundant vibration sensor could be used for utility evaluations [114].

3.1.3. Parametric dependencies

As illustrated in Figure 5a by the colored columns, we assume damage happens in the first, second, and last floor columns via modifying their stiffness and the stiffness k of Equation (13) in the corresponding links. Furthermore, we do not consider as dependencies any of the properties used to define the perturbed FOM, namely the Young modulus

E and density ρ , to ensure model-form errors are properly introduced in the testing signals. The parameter vector \mathbf{p} used for training and model derivation (Algorithm 1) is $\mathbf{p} = [\alpha, k_{1-3}, \lambda_{1-4}]$, where the input accelerogram is modeled as $\text{Input} = \lambda_1 * \{\text{Kobe}\} + \lambda_2 * \{\text{Northridge}\} + \lambda_3 * \{\text{El Centro}\} + \lambda_4 * \{\text{Morgan}\}$ and all reference seismograms are repeated twice in time. The parameter vector $\boldsymbol{\mu} \subseteq \mathbf{p}$ to be inferred during operation (Algorithm 2) is $\boldsymbol{\mu} = [\alpha, k_1, k_2, k_3, \lambda]$, where k_i indicates the stiffness coefficient for floor i and λ is a scaling parameter of the input accelerogram, formulated as $\text{Input} = (1 - \lambda) * \{\text{Kobe} + \text{Northridge}\} + \lambda * \{\text{El Centro} + \text{Morgan}\}$, where all reference accelerograms are repeated twice in time. As mentioned, α is a characteristic parameter representing the post-yield to elastic stiffness ratio and permanent damage in a system typically changes k_i [109]. However, changing α along k_i is a conscious choice here to elevate the difficulty and simulate different frame instances. For every testing sequence, α assumes the same value in all damage events. The range and distribution of the parameters employed are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3: System properties and range of parameter values for the training and inference stage of the framework.

Parameter:	$\lambda, \lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, \lambda_4 (\times 1.5e^6)$	$k_1, k_2, k_3 (\times 1e^{10})$	α	β	γ	δ_η, δ_v	A, w
Range:	[0.1, 1.0]	[0.3, 1.0]	[0.1, 0.9]	3.0	2.0	0.0	1.0

3.1.4. Performance evaluation in example scenario

An example testing scenario is discussed herein. The testing ground motion accelerogram is depicted in Figure 6. The testing scenario includes five damage events, illustrated with red dashed lines in Figure 6. To produce the monitoring signals used for testing, the perturbed FOM in Table 1 is simulated under the given input accelerogram and parametric traits, as described in Algorithm 1.

The frame is initially assumed healthy ($\alpha = k_{1-3} = 1.0$) and the proposed framework is recursively employed to infer $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ and deliver the optimal model given the input utility function. Specifically, after damage event A, α becomes 0.30 and the k_{1-3} stiffness coefficients change while the operator has chosen a balanced utility function ($\gamma = 0.5$). Although changing α is not a realistic assumption, this is a deliberate choice here to elevate the difficulty and cause abrupt damage via the nonlinear springs. This happens only during the first damage event, α remains the same afterward. Then, the stiffness coefficients reduce unevenly reflecting localized damage and the operator modifies the utility function to first favor efficiency (after event B, $\gamma = 0.3$) and then accuracy (after event D, $\gamma = 0.8$) while also changing the monitored QoI (Eq. 11). Lastly, event X reduces all stiffness coefficients k_{1-3} to values outside the operational regime of Table 3 that was considered for deriving the ROMs and HROMs. This extreme case is designed to challenge the accuracy of the available reduced representations and test whether the framework will signal a retraining step for the derived models.

In Figure 7 the framework’s performance in parameter inference is reported for the optimal HROM with $\{\tau, r\} = \{1e^{-3}, 8\}$. The UKF delivers similar accuracy for all ROM and HROM resolutions considered. This further underscores the importance of using a utility function as the key metric for model selection, as it balances fidelity and efficiency according to the needs of the operator and the downstream task. As shown in all sub-figures of Figure 7, the proposed framework recovers the underlying true parameter values after the damage events. The framework’s performance is illustrated for all events excluding the introduced extreme event X, which cannot be captured using the underlying pre-trained model resolutions. It’s worth noting that the monitoring setup and the range of the parameters has been chosen so that the system remains observable, the input excitation has been scaled accordingly to excite the underlying nonlinearities, and the UKF utilizes the variance of the underlying optimal model to readjust its initial state covariances and process noise as soon as convergence is observed.

The utility readings for the example scenario in Figure 6 are shown in Figure 8. The framework effectively tracks system state changes by recursively inferring the corresponding parametric traits, updating the underlying model representations, and identifying the optimal model for downstream tasks. From the considered model resolutions only the HROM can be evaluated in real-time. Given the relatively low dimensionality of this benchmark example, the ROM utilities are also retrieved in near real-time. The corresponding exact timings are reported in detail in Table 4 at the end of this section. All considered model resolutions achieve a relatively high utility in recovering the target QoIs before the extreme event X, aside from minor low-amplitude oscillations following the pattern of the UKF inference before convergence is achieved. Furthermore, the consistently high utility values before the utility QoI change in event

Figure 6: Example input accelerogram with damage events indicated by red lines. Initially the frame is assumed undamaged ($\alpha = k_{1-3} = 1.0$), the inter-story drift is the QoI (Table 2), and the operator has chosen a balanced utility ($\gamma = 0.5$ in Eq. 10). After event B, the operator prioritizes fast decisions ($\gamma = 0.3$). After event D, the operator modifies the monitored QoI to be the restoring force \mathbf{R} in a link of interest and prioritizes accuracy ($\gamma = 0.8$). Event X is modeled as an extreme damage event to demonstrate the performance limits of the underlying ROMs and HROMs.

446 D confirm the robustness and reliability of the HROM in delivering real-time accurate predictions under parametric
 448 variability. Following the utility changes introduced by the operator in event D, the ROM emerges as the optimal
 450 model for downstream tasks. This happens because the accuracy of the HROM deteriorates slightly when recovering
 452 internal quantities such as stresses and strains due to the hyper-reduction approximation and its real-time efficiency is
 454 underplayed for the sake of demonstration. The FOM produces equally high utility readings due to the high-fidelity
 456 requirement ($\gamma = 0.8$), however, it can be considered only for post-earthquake tasks given its slow evaluation time.

452 Following the extreme damage event X, only the FOM maintains sufficient accuracy for decision-making while
 454 the utility of both the ROMs and HROMs deteriorates significantly. While physics-based ROMs are known to exhibit
 456 good extrapolation capabilities, such a performance deterioration under extreme events is expected and event X has
 458 been introduced to illustrate this. Consequently, the proposed framework correctly identifies that the FOM should
 be selected when high-fidelity predictions are required. However, the FOM utility readings will not be available
 to the operator in (near) real-time, given its low computational efficiency. Therefore, the proposed scheme allows the
 operator to introduce an appropriate threshold—as illustrated in Figures 4- that serves as a signaling mechanism for
 performance deterioration and subsequent actions that might involve retraining the underlying model(s).

460 The real-time response approximation in the top right unmeasured node of the top floor in Figure 5a is reported
 462 in Figure 9 using the HROM. The HROM delivers a sufficiently accurate performance, adapting to the underlying
 464 damage via the UKF updates. Furthermore, the probabilistic components of the framework enable the quantification
 466 of the uncertainty in the predicted response. To achieve this, the UKF posterior estimates and the probabilistic latent
 468 space of the HROM are sampled and uncertainty is propagated to the obtained estimates by evaluating the response
 for each sampled realization. These evaluations are executed in parallel, maintaining computational efficiency. In
 addition, the use of the Unscented Transform as detailed in section 2.2.3 offers an efficient strategy for an initial
 comprehensive understanding of the errors involved. Although the resulting error bounds in Figure 9 will not neces-
 sarily encapsulate perfectly the observed response due to model-form errors and noise, they capture the most critical
 maximum amplitude regions and provide a direct measure of predictive reliability relevant for decision-making.

470 A zoomed view of the response approximation quality for the underlying ROM and HROM is offered in Figure 10.
 472 By design and as expected, the ROM delivers a more accurate performance, especially in high-frequency regimes.
 However, the improvement is minuscule and when weighted with computational runtime, the HROM outperforms it
 and delivers a higher utility as illustrated in Figure 8. In contrast, the ROM delivers a substantially increased precision

Figure 7: Parameter inference using the UKF and the HROM. Dotted black lines indicate the damage events (A-D), following Figure 6. Dashed red lines indicate the ground truth values.

Figure 8: Total utility readings for the considered model resolutions. The operator defined QoI and utility weight γ (Eq. 10) is also reported along with the two damage events.

when tasked to recover internal structural quantities such as stresses or joint forces. This is exemplified in Figure 11, where the HROM struggles to capture the restoring force of the hysteretic links with the same degree of accuracy as the acceleration response. As a result, the ROM emerges as the optimal model after event D in Figure 8 given the

Figure 9: Acceleration response approximation in the top right unmeasured node A in Figure 5a using the HROM.

Figure 10: Comparison of the acceleration response approximation in the top right unmeasured node A in Figure 5a.

476 operator choice to prioritize accuracy (set $\gamma = 0.8$) and define the maximum stress as the QoI.

3.1.5. Performance evaluation in testing set

478 To evaluate the performance of the proposed framework in a robust manner, a testing set of 500 parametric configurations μ is created. Each testing scenario follows the setup discussed in Table 2 and Figure 6 with only the first two damage events, namely A and B. The performance of the optimal model for each resolution across the testing scenarios is summarized in Table 4. The FOM was not used for inference inside the UKF given its high computational load. Instead, FOM model runs were evaluated with the inferred parameters from the ROM to report timings for comparison purposes. The timings reported in Table 4 exclude the parallelization of FE assembly evaluations and forward model runs inside the UKF. It is important to clarify here that the primary challenge is not strict millisecond-level

(a) ROM restoring force approximation

(b) HROM restoring force approximation

Figure 11: Comparison of the restoring force approximation (Eq. 13) in node B in Figure 5a.

486 real-time response but rather fast but reliable model updating under evolving system conditions over longer opera-
 488 tional horizons, as in many digital twin applications for engineering infrastructure. Thus, real-time considerations are
 490 contextualized accordingly and aspects such as communication latency typically play a secondary role compared to
 the issues demonstrated here: model discrepancy, environmental variability, and parameter drift. The proposed frame-
 work is therefore designed to support continuous data assimilation and adaptive model selection as new monitoring
 data become available, rather than requiring instantaneous synchronization between the physical and virtual systems.

Table 4: Performance measures across testing configurations. The average and maximum error is reported for the optimal configuration of each resolution. No parallelization is assumed.

	Fidelity Measures					Efficiency Timings (per monitored s)				
	$\ \mu - \hat{\mu}\ $		\ddot{u} RMSE		Utility	Model run		UKF Inference		Utility
	Mean	Max	Mean	Max	Average	Time	Speedup	(per sigma point)	Total	Mean
FOM	<1%	2%	15%	20%	0.98	1.52s	1.0	-	-	0.73
ROM	2%	4%	20%	24%	0.93	0.55s	3.8	2.82	285s	0.94
HROM	4%	10%	24%	29%	0.91	0.11s	13.5	0.52s	56s	0.99

3.2. Simplified fuselage panel

492 The second numerical example concerns a simplified fuselage panel, a representative load-carrying component in
 494 both maritime and aerospace structures, and therefore of broad practical relevance. This example is loosely inspired
 496 by [115], where dynamic substructuring was applied to analyze cracking in thin-walled aeronautic structures. Here,
 we adopt and extend the implementation proposed in [18] for model assembly, modifying it to account for bolted
 connections and large deformations leading to geometric nonlinearities [116, 117, 118].

3.2.1. Decision support scenario

498 The following scenario is defined: An asset operator needs decision support in real-time related to structural con-
 500 dition monitoring following boundary damage. Furthermore, material properties of the asset are uncertain prior to
 502 deployment. Thus, the operator first utilizes the proposed framework under low-amplitude vibration data correspond-
 ing to regular operation to calibrate the parametric traits of the underlying ROM and HROM considered. This initial
 calibration phase showcases how the generic parametrization introduced in the underlying models can be exploited
 to account for potential model form discrepancies. Fidelity is prioritized here, until the models are calibrated and

504 capable for (near) real-time inference. In turn, the stochastic excitation amplitude is increased to induce damage, rep-
 506 resenting more intensive operational conditions. We further assume that the asset operator defines a utility function
 508 that favors efficiency after the initial calibration, reflecting the need for real-time decision making under intensive
 510 operation related to proactive actions. After the damage event, the framework updates the underlying models and the
 512 operator gets notified. As a result, they switch to a utility that favors fidelity to decide on the criticality of the damage
 and the potential need for replacing the panel or fixing the bolted connections. The monitoring setup, summarized
 in Table 5, includes eight acceleration sensors placed at distinct nodes (blue dots in Figure 12a), each recording ac-
 celeration along the excitation direction. These measurements are used for the parameter inference task. A redundant
 sensor (sensor 9, shown in red in Figure 12a) provides independent data to trigger adaptive model selection and assess
 model fidelity.

Table 5: Details of the monitoring setup for the fuselage panel. Damage events are modeled by varying the stiffness of the bolted joints and the panel. Max QoIs are evaluated in rolling windows of 0.2 seconds.

Scenario	Panel and bolted joints get damaged. Input utility changes to reflect different downstream tasks.
Objective	Given the operator defined utility, select the optimal model at any given time.
Utility function(s)	Equations 10-12, Figure 4, $t_{max} = 100s, w_1 = 3, w_2 = 1, \epsilon_{max} = 50\%$
Utility function variations	Calibration phase $\rightarrow \gamma = 0.8$, QoI=Deflection at sensor 9 (red dot in Fig. 12a) Utility change A $\rightarrow \gamma = 0.3$, QoI= Max \ddot{u} at sensor 9 Damage event A $\rightarrow \gamma = 0.3$, QoI=Max \ddot{u} at sensor 9 Damage event B & Util. change B $\rightarrow \gamma = 0.9$, QoI=Max stress at boundary
Monitoring data	Nodal accelerations Eight nodes monitored (blue dots in Fig. 12a)

514 3.2.2. Numerical model setup

516 The fuselage panel geometry, boundary conditions, loading, and sensor layout are shown in Figure 12a. The
 518 panel is cylindrical with a radius of 2.5 m and a uniform thickness of 3 mm. An aluminum material is assumed, with
 520 a variable density ρ and Young’s modulus E_p introduced to amplify large deformations and thus capture geometric
 522 nonlinearities. Unlike previous studies employing free-free or fully fixed conditions, the present setup applies fixed
 524 boundary conditions only along the left edge. Along the right edge we use multi point constraints and spring elements
 to model the bolts. This is a simplified assumption for a computationally efficient FE assembly, assuming that bolt
 stresses are not the focus. Contact effects are not incorporated and the interested reader is referred to [119, 120, 121].
 Furthermore, the stiffness coefficients k_1, k_2, k_3 , of the springs materializing the bolts are varied to represent loosening
 effects. In Figure 12b one of the hyper-reduced meshes is illustrated, with more highlighted elements on the boundary
 and the middle of the panel, where nonlinear behavior is dominant.

526 3.2.3. Parametric dependencies

528 The system properties and the parametric dependencies of the model are summarized in Table 6. A dynamic
 530 pressure load is applied uniformly, following a white-noise-like signal with parametric magnitude M in the frequency
 532 range [40, 250] Hz. During training, the parameter vector \mathbf{p} used in Algorithm 1 is $\mathbf{p} = [\rho, E_p, k_1, k_2, k_3, M]$ and every
 534 training sample is excited using a different seed for generating the white-noise excitation. After deployment, all system
 parameters excluding the amplitude coefficient M get calibrated using low-amplitude vibration data corresponding to
 normal operation. Next, the operator expecting a more intense loading event changes the required utility to prioritize
 fast decision-making for proactive actions, as described in Table 5. From that point onward, the parameter vector
 $\boldsymbol{\mu} \subseteq \mathbf{p}$ to be inferred in Algorithm 2 becomes $\boldsymbol{\mu} = [E_p, k_1, k_2, k_3]$. The material parameter E_p can simulate potential
 damage on the fuselage and influence the geometrically nonlinear behavior directly. Similarly, parameters k_1, k_2, k_3
 control the rigidity of the boundary and can model bolt loosening or equivalent damage events in a simplified manner.

Figure 12: Simplified fuselage panel geometry, loading, sensor locations and ECSW reduced mesh. The blue sensors are used for inference while the red redundant sensor is employed for utility evaluation.

Table 6: System properties and range of parametric traits.

Parameter:	E_p ($\times 25 \text{ GPa}$)	k_1, k_2, k_3 ($\times 1e^{16}$)	M	Poisson's ratio	Density ($\times 2700 \text{ kg/m}^3$)
Range:	[1.0, 2.0]	[0.1, 1.0]	[0.1, 1.0]	$\nu = 0.3$	$\rho = [0.5, 1.0]$

3.2.4. Performance evaluation in example scenario

The testing scenario consists of a four-second calibration phase under normal operational conditions, followed by two damage events, as summarized in Table 5. As explained, this setup is selected to exemplify the use of the proposed framework in a case study with several uncertain input traits that dictate prior model calibration of the ROMs generic parametric formulation. The input pressure excitation is considered known and is reported in Figure 13 along with the utility changes introduced by the operator and the damage events. During the calibration phase, all parametric traits of the underlying models are updated. The two damage events introduce global panel damage by decreasing E_p and bolt loosening effects by reducing all corresponding stiffness coefficients $k_1 - k_3$. Thus, density ρ is fixed following the calibration phase. Model updating during the initial phase is also done using the proposed framework and the UKF and a four second duration is only used for demonstration purposes. In scenarios where long response sequences are available and more system parameters require calibration offline Bayesian model updating techniques can also be employed, eg. the iTMCMC [122]. The stochastic excitation sequence in Figure 13 is produced using a different random seed than the ones used during testing and its amplitude coefficient $M_{test} = 0.90$.

Following deployment and operation as summarized in Algorithm 2, the framework employs the underlying HROM with $\{\tau, r\} = \{1e^{-2}, 8\}$ to perform model updating and parameter inference, as illustrated in Figure 14. This HROM is selected as the optimal one as it is the most efficient in terms of runtime due to the hyper-reduction approximation and delivers a satisfying accuracy. Thus, it delivers the maximum utility, at least before damage event B, and UKF-powered parameter inference results are demonstrated using this resolution as a predictive simulator. The proposed framework efficiently recovers all underlying parameter values both during the calibration phase and after the two damage events, as observed in Figure 14. The QoI modified by the operator after the second damage event B does not influence the performance of the underlying models, as the UKF still employs the redundant acceleration measurement for the likelihood function as described in Table 5. The noisy oscillations around the true value for all parameters in Figure 14 are attributed to a) the use of the noisy acceleration measurements for the likelihood, b) model discrepancies that cause response deviations, c) the relatively high parameter noise used to encourage the UKF to explore the parameter domain, which is critical when parameter shifts occur and the model needs to adapt, and d) the UKF tuning that might not be optimal.

Figure 13: Input pressure excitation. The first four seconds indicate regular conditions and the operator calibrates the parameters of the models, before the utility changes to prioritize fast decisions ($\gamma = 0.3$). After the damage event B at 8 seconds, the operator modifies the monitored QoI and prioritizes accuracy ($\gamma = 0.9$).

562 Despite these minor discrepancies, the proposed framework converges in the true values relatively fast and allows
 563 updates the utilized models accordingly to allow for real-time response inference. This is further validated by the total
 564 utility values reported in Figure 15. The HROM provides hyper-accelerated model evaluations while maintaining
 565 acceptable accuracy, thus yielding the highest utility values until damage event B. Even though fidelity is prioritized
 566 during the calibration phase, the operator has defined deflection as the QoI and the underlying HROMs maintains high
 567 accuracy in recovering the true values. The jumps observed in time windows where the utility remains constant are
 568 attributed to the different over- and underestimation weights w_1 and w_2 . After event B, the operator prioritizes accuracy
 569 and requests high-fidelity insight on the maximum boundary stress value by changing the QoI and setting $\gamma = 0.90$
 570 in Equation (10). As a result, the framework outputs a finer HROM resolution, namely $HROM_{fine}$ with $\{\tau, r\} =$
 571 $\{1e^{-3}, 8\}$ as the optimal model, closely followed by the ROM with $r = 8$. This is expected since parameter τ controls
 572 the quality of the sparse weighted hyper-reduction approximation discussed in section 2.2.4 up to an extent, and tighter
 573 minimization boundaries can deliver higher fidelity HROMs. In addition, hyper-reduction is a second-tier, sparse
 574 weighted approximation that introduces errors, especially in quantities that are directly related with the reconstruction
 575 of the nonlinear terms. Thus, the ROM might deliver higher accuracy estimates at times. It is worth noting here
 576 that numerical parameters such as $\{\tau, r\}$ might be a priori chosen effectively and not necessarily vary, or their change
 577 might not yield substantially different results. This is shown in Figure 15 where both HROM resolutions deliver
 578 high utility values before the second damage event. However, this case study has been designed to exemplify a
 579 scenario where efficiency is downplayed and the most lightweight representation available might yield lower fidelity
 580 estimates than required, as observed after the damage event B. This further highlights the importance of the utility-
 581 based formulation proposed, which quantitatively balances competing attributes and enables data-informed model
 582 selection and validation.

583 Following the model updating and selection process, the framework is employed for response prediction. Owing to
 584 its physics-aware formulation, the optimal models selected can recover quantities of interest across all physical fields
 585 at any given time. In addition, by combining parameter uncertainty with draws from the model's probabilistic latent
 586 space via the Unscented Transform, as discussed in section 2.2.3, the employed cVAE propagates the uncertainty to the
 587 estimates and provides error bounds that account for uncertainty in the reduced representation itself. The acceleration
 588 response prediction for the optimal HROM resolution is shown in Figure 16. The approximation is reported for
 589 Sensor 9 in Figure 12a, which was not considered in the UKF inference task. In this example, the resulting error
 590 bounds envelope the underlying response, rendering the obtained approximation trustworthy even if the obtained

Figure 14: Parameter inference using the UKF and the HROM. Dotted black lines indicate the damage events (A&B), following Figure 13. Dashed red lines indicate the ground truth values.

Figure 15: Utility evaluation for the considered model resolutions. The operator defined QoI and utility weight γ (Eq. 10) are also reported. Model $HROM_{fine}$ has $\{\tau, r\} = \{1e^{-3}, 8\}$ and $HROM$ has $\{\tau, r\} = \{1e^{-2}, 8\}$.

mean approximation does not capture the underlying response exactly.

592 The obtained acceleration response approximation is reported in more detail for two dedicated time windows of the calibration and normal operation phase in Figure 17. This magnified view provides a more clear evaluation of

Figure 16: Acceleration response approximation in the redundant sensor 9 indicated by the red circle in Figure 12a. Sensor 9 is not used for inference in the UKF.

594 the performance of the proposed framework and its ability to recover the underlying response while balancing fidelity
 596 and efficiency as requested by the operator. Uncertainty bounds are also illustrated for both time windows. During
 598 calibration, output uncertainty is higher and the error bounds in Figure 17a are wider. This is mainly attributed to the
 low amplitude excitation of the calibration phase and the model being trained in a wide range of excitation amplitudes.
 The uncertainty bounds after calibration become relatively narrower since the testing excitation amplitude ($M = 0.9$)
 is towards the upper end of the training set in Table 6.

Figure 17: Magnified view of the acceleration response approximation in the redundant sensor 9 indicated by the red circle in Figure 12a. Sensor 9 is not used for inference in the UKF.

3.2.5. Performance evaluation in testing set

To evaluate the performance of the proposed framework in a robust manner, a testing set of 500 parametric configurations μ is created. Each testing scenario also has a different excitation amplitude M , follows the setup discussed in Table 5 and Figure 13 and the calibration phase of Figure 13. The performance of the framework is summarized in Table 7. Similar to the shear-frame case study, the FOM was not used for inference inside the UKF given its high computational load. Instead, FOM model runs were evaluated with the inferred parameters from the ROM to report timings. The timings reported in Table 7 exclude the parallelization of the forward model runs inside the UKF. To demonstrate absolute the real-time inference potential 50 computational cores were used for the proposed framework to deliver the requested utilities in a matter of seconds. However, as already clarified for the shear frame, the primary challenge addressed here is fast and reliable model updating under evolving system conditions over the asset’s operational horizon, as it is the case in many engineering infrastructure twinning applications. Thus, real-time considerations require proper contextualization, and aspects such as communication latency or instantaneous synchronization between the physical and virtual systems typically play a secondary role compared to the issues discussed, namely model discrepancy, environmental variability, and parameter drift.

As summarized in Table 7, the framework effectively balances computational efficiency and accuracy, delivering highly consistent response estimates on average. Moreover, the probabilistic formulation and embedded Bayesian components enable the framework to provide confidence bounds that enclose the true response, as exemplified in Figure 17. Furthermore, the framework flexibly allows the decision-maker to define a total or fidelity utility threshold to automatically trigger model retraining in real time, avoiding delays associated with full FOM evaluations. This approach mitigates local minima in utility evaluations and high-error cases, as exemplified in Figure 8.

Table 7: Performance across testing configurations. No parallelization is assumed. The average utility with respect to model fidelity is presented separately for the different user requirements reported in Table 5.

	Fidelity Measures				Efficiency Timings (per monitored s)				
	$\ \mu - \hat{\mu}\ $		Average Utility		Model run		UKF Inference		Utility
	Mean	Max	(4s-8s)	(8s-10s)	Time	Speedup	(per sigma point)	Total	Mean
FOM	<1%	<1%	0.99	0.95	27.7s	1.0	-	-	0.47
ROM	2%	3%	0.98	0.92	6.75s	4.1	21.88s	2123s	0.79
HROM	6%	10%	0.95	0.86	0.39s	69.6	1.1s	104s	0.99
HROM _{fine}	6%	9%	0.96	0.90	1.42s	19.0	3.0s	292s	0.95

4. Discussion

The developed framework addresses a central challenge in real-time O&M, SHM, and decision support—the adaptive selection of the lowest-cost model capable of delivering predictions of the required fidelity under evolving conditions. At its core, the proposed framework integrates a generative reduced-order modeling scheme, conditioned on parametric inputs, with a Bayesian inference layer that recursively estimates the underlying system parameters from sensing data. This combination enables continuous model adaptation, quantifies prediction confidence, and supports decision-making through a utility-based formulation that balances two competing attributes: (i) model fidelity and (ii) computational efficiency. In principle, the asset operator retains the flexibility to define the utility function or the importance weights of the competing attributes based on the task at hand, which leads to a scheme with increased serviceability for higher-level frameworks. By maximizing the expected utility, the framework identifies the fit-for-purpose model at each time step, determining whether to accept, switch, or retrain a candidate representation.

Two numerical case studies—a hysteretic shear frame with uneven damage and a geometrically nonlinear fuselage panel—demonstrate the framework’s ability to select optimal model resolutions and adapt to changing system conditions. The approach reliably identifies when reduced-order models lose validity and retraining is required, particularly during extreme events beyond the training domain. Moreover, the probabilistic formulation provides uncertainty quantification, generating response confidence bounds that capture the true behavior even under low-precision conditions. Furthermore, the use of the *VpROM*, a conditional Variational Autoencoder-boosted ROM, is not a constraint for the proposed framework. The proposed framework is intentionally designed to remain agnostic to the specific

638 surrogate or reduced-order representation adopted. However, certain limitations ought to be acknowledged, which, in
639 turn, outline avenues for future exploration.

640 First, the proposed framework is demonstrated through numerical case studies. The primary objective of the
641 present work is the methodological verification of a complete adaptive twinning pipeline operating under streaming
642 monitoring data and evolving operational objectives. In particular, the contribution focuses on establishing the con-
643 sistency and robustness of the interaction between parametrized reduced-order representations, recursive Bayesian in-
644 ference, utility-driven model selection, uncertainty propagation, and online adaptation. In our view, such verification
645 constitutes a necessary prerequisite before transitioning toward experimental and industrial-scale deployment studies,
646 where additional sources of uncertainty and operational complexity arise. To partially emulate realistic deployment
647 conditions, the present work adopts a perturbed FOM strategy introducing combined forms of discrepancy through
648 modified discretizations, spatially varying material properties, density perturbations, and noisy monitoring signals.
649 While such perturbations cannot replace experimental validation, they nevertheless provide a controlled mechanism
650 for introducing model-form mismatch, parametric variability, and sensing uncertainty beyond purely synthetic noise-
651 corrupted simulations. Experimental and field validation therefore constitute important next steps toward operational
652 deployment and are planned as part of future work.

653 Second, the framework assumes that all relevant physics are represented within the available models. This is
654 related to both extreme phenomena that have not been considered during training, and to unmeasured model dis-
655 turbances when deploying the framework in real monitoring data. In these settings, the proposed framework will
656 signal the need for model retraining, which is expected. A fully adaptive treatment is needed to explicitly handle such
657 unforeseen or unmodeled phenomena, where even high-fidelity models may yield low utility—a challenge pointing
658 toward self-evolving digital representations. However, even if online retraining or fully adaptive updating is consid-
659 ered and the additional computational overhead and stability considerations are addressed, the resulting scheme might
660 also under-perform so the issue of potential model failure remains and the proposed framework is equipped with the
661 utility-based criteria to signal this in time.

662 Third, the parametric formulations employed may not fully capture effects such as excitation frequency content
663 or mode interactions; these aspects will be explored alongside the extension toward self-evolving model structures.
664 Fourth, the framework’s computational scalability is demonstrated empirically in Tables 4 & 7, which span different
665 system sizes across the two case studies. The FOM cost scales with the full-order dimension n , while the ROM
666 compresses the linear system to $r \ll n$. The residual bottleneck in the nonlinear term assembly, which scales with
667 the element count n_e , is removed by the HROM via hyper-reduction by restricting the assembly to $k \ll n_e$ elements.
668 The UKF cost scales with the sigma-point count that combines the reduced state dimension with the dimension of the
669 inferred parameter vector. The low dimensionality of the underlying ROM or HROM is therefore central to online
670 tractability, as it bounds both the per-evaluation cost and the augmented state within real-time-feasible ranges. Beyond
671 this, nested inference schemes might be needed in the case of large parameter dimensionality, and specialized matrix
672 projection techniques for increased efficiency given the sparse nature of the underlying matrices.

673 Fifth, the proposed work focuses on a central challenge in many digital twin applications for engineering infras-
674 tructure, namely the fast and reliable model updating under evolving system conditions over the asset’s operational
675 horizons. Real-time consideration refer to this setting and strict millisecond-level response or instantaneous synchro-
676 nization between the physical and virtual systems are not discussed in detail as they typically play a secondary role
677 compared to issues such as model discrepancy, environmental variability, and parameter drift. We acknowledge this
678 limitation along with the fact that practical deployment of such frameworks in industrial environments would require
679 addressing additional system-integration aspects, such as edge–cloud data management, latency and synchronization
680 mechanisms, computational infrastructure, and long-term operational constraints. Although such aspects may not be
681 directly related to the pipeline’s formulation, they might influence its online performance, and a detailed treatment
682 (e.g., OPC-UA communication layers or hardware-in-the-loop integration) is left for future work.

683 Finally, the proposed framework primarily targets structural and mechanical infrastructure assets represented by
684 dynamical systems with bounded parametric variability, such as buildings, bridges, and aerospace or mechanical com-
685 ponents, where physics-based reduced-order modeling remains both meaningful and computationally advantageous.
686 Intermediate cases involving multi-physics couplings, varying boundary conditions, or moderate topology changes
687 may still be accommodated through suitable extensions of the underlying ROMs, such as domain-decomposition tech-
688 niques, adaptive parametrizations, or mesh-morphing, without modifying the utility-driven model-selection layer.

Data Availability

The models and data supporting this study's findings are available from the author **KV** upon reasonable request.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Konstantinos Vlachas: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Writing. **Antonios Kamariotis**: Methodology, Software. **Eleni Chatzi**: Resources, Writing - review & editing.

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